

Rec Lit

Un blog sobre reciclaje literario postdigital

MENÚ

Digital Humanities Tools for Germanic Literary Studies: A Project Report by Dominika Anna Gortych and Cezary Rosiński

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The work carried out at the [Digital Humanities Centre](#) (Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences) in the field of computational research within literature and culture has attracted the attention of scholars of various philologies, including Germanic philology ([Instytut Filologii Germańskiej UAM](#)). As part of my literary research on contemporary German literature, I submitted a project entitled [Right-wing violence after 1989](#)

the National Science Centre ([NCN](#)). I received a decision on its financing in the summer of 2024.

The project aimed to examine how violence inspired by right-wing ideology is portrayed in contemporary literature, particularly prose describing the experiences of the younger generation in eastern Germany after 1989 — a period often referred to as the ‘Baseball Bat Years’ (*Baseballschlägerjahre*). The research aimed to confirm or refute the assumption that the stories of perpetrators dominate literary discourse today, while the experiences of victims, particularly those intersecting with other forms of exclusion (e.g. racism or sexism), remain marginalised.

To date, no research has been conducted that comprehensively addresses this topic by taking into account both perpetrators and victims of violence. Additionally, there has been an absence of a bibliography containing commentary that would facilitate the development of a contemporary body of literary works focusing on right-wing violence and enable a re-evaluation of existing research assumptions.

The project, therefore, involved creating a publicly accessible digital database that complies with FAIR principles. This database collects information about novels and short stories written since 1989 that address the issue of right-wing violence. The objectives were:

- to collect a corpus of literary texts on this phenomenon;
- to identify the ideological contexts of violence (e.g. neo-Nazism, racism and sexism) and its various forms (physical, psychological, verbal and sexual);
- The authors of these texts were to be characterised, as were the conditions of their publication and reception (e.g. place of publication, type of publisher, awards received).

The whole programming code is publicly available in a GitHub repository. The README file is accessible [here](#).

Stages of project implementation

I began the project with a week-long search at the Staatsbibliothek Berlin. Using the library's resources, including its digital press archive, I compiled a list of 45 novels about right-wing violence since 1989 that have attracted the attention of literary critics and researchers. Based on my research, I compiled a list of 125 keywords that accurately reflected the phenomenon under study. I then grouped this catalogue according to the following provisional categories: name of historical event; place of event; terms/synonyms for violence; concepts describing social phenomena; right-wing extremism; post-migration; youth culture; and historical figures.

For the second stage of the research, I collaborated with Cezary Rosiński, who is a documentary specialist and data expert at the Current Bibliography Laboratory of the Polish Academy of Sciences. He is also a literary scholar and Python programmer. This opened the project up to digital humanities tools. Based on an existing catalogue of keywords, I commissioned Cezary to automatically search the available resources of perlentaucher.de, a digital archive containing information on most literary texts published in Germany, as well as advertising texts, novel summaries, and reviews. This gave us a list of 5,000 texts published after 1989 whose descriptions contained the aforementioned keywords. Such a rich collection required revision and reduction, which took place in the following steps: First, we marked the literary texts that had been selected on the basis of the preliminary query in Berlin, as well as a similar number of negative examples. Second,

Cezary developed a Python code to identify further texts that corresponded to the project's criteria. We obtained a list of 148 texts. However, as the code was only 80% accurate, we decided to verify the results (analysis of keywords assigned to each item, analysis of press reviews, and any available theoretical and literary studies). Ultimately, the corpus comprised 113 items.

The third stage of the research project involved creating an RDF (Resource Description Framework) database that stores represented information as triples — subject, predicate, and object — enabling semantic representation and processing of interconnected data in the Semantic Web. The triple structure allows you to store information about, among other things, authorship: Als wir träumten by Clemens Meyer

(<<https://example.org/rechtsextremismus/Text/n102>> — schema:author —

<<https://example.org/rechtsextremismus/Person/a75>>),

awards: Reinhard Jirgl awarded the Alfred-Döblin-Preis

(<<https://example.org/rechtsextremismus/Person/a16>> — schema:award —

<<https://example.org/rechtsextremismus/Prize/pr62>>) or

scope of activity: Blumenbar Verlag with a reach of 'local/independent'

(<<https://example.org/rechtsextremismus/Organization/i8>> — schema:areaServed — 'local/independent'). Our

resource contains bibliographical and research metadata as well as external identifiers, not only to ensure greater compliance with the FAIR principles, but also to encourage researchers to data- and metadata-driven research within literary studies. This database enables queries with SPARQL and Cypher languages for answering more sophisticated research questions. This purposefully designed information resource about literary texts was created through a series of automated activities on the website

perlentaucher.de using digital humanities technologies, such as bibliographic data modelling using Linked Open Data (LOD), text mining with Natural Language Processing tools, and network analysis using NetworkX, combined with manual expert annotation to supplement information unavailable in external knowledge sources (e.g. perspectives on right-wing violence and the ideological contexts and types of violence). Unfortunately, we did not have digital versions of all literary texts. Therefore, we decided to analyse the information contained on the perlentaucher.de website, i.e. metadata for each novel, paratexts (publishing advertisements, or ‘Klappentexte’) and summaries of publishing reviews contained on the website. The following entities were defined and assigned appropriate attributes: [I] Literary text: title, date of publication, place of publication, publisher, genre; debut/subsequent novel; theme/perspective of the issue (generational, intersectional, or other), cause of violence, type of violence, keywords and reviews. [II] Person: first and last name, dates of birth and death, along with places of birth and death; gender, awards received, professions, and historical background. [III] Place: name and coordinates. [IV] Award: name and date. [V] Institution: name of publisher, date of establishment, and reach. Where possible, we assigned VIAF and Wikidata IDs to entities to enhance interoperability of the resource and to promote LOD. All automatically obtained results were reviewed. The database has been published under a CC BY 4.0 licence in open access in the [Zenodo repository](#), and a copy has also been deposited in the [AmuRed](#) research data repository.

Project results

The corpus and database enable the tracking of relationships between issues, authors, and literary institutions, which contributes to the research’s innovative

nature. The resource prepared in this way made it possible to answer an extensive set of research questions focusing on the analysis of literature on 'rechte Gewalt' (right-wing violence) in terms of quantity, time, content and literary forms, publications and distribution, and the role of visualisation in literary studies.

Number of books on right-wing violence per year, depending on perspective

Number of books / Publication's Year

Analysing the semantic relationships between the identified entities partially confirmed the hypothesis that narratives about right-wing violence in generational terms predominate in literary texts over those that allow for an intersectional approach to this issue. However, it should be noted that, since 2020, there has been a noticeable increase in the number of texts of the second type. Throughout the entire study period, texts were published that could not be assigned to any of the designated perspectives. However, based on the collected data, it was not possible to unequivocally revise the hypothesis about the predominance of interest from the perspective of perpetrators of violence. This is because even among texts describing violence as a generational experience, narratives from the perspective of victims were found. Furthermore, the collected data did not always allow the

The ten most popular keywords in novels about right-wing violence in the years 1990–2025

Keywords: violence, neo-Nazis, right wing, racism, reunification, GDR, provinces, NSU, right-wing extremism, conflict

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In conclusion, this project has not only achieved its research goals but also established a replicable workflow that can serve as a model for future initiatives. By consciously creating reusable resources for the academic community and ensuring access to robust analytical tools, it responds to some of the most pressing needs in contemporary literary studies. Such an approach fosters openness, collaboration, and methodological innovation—values that are essential for the continued growth and relevance of the discipline.

Dominika Anna Gortych and Cezary Rosiński

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